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Oxodiperoxomolybdenum complex immobilized onto ionic liquid modified SBA-15 as an effective catalysis for sulfide oxidation to sulfoxides using hydrogen peroxide

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ABSTRACT

A supported ionic-liquid-phase (SILP) was prepared by the reaction of 1-methyl-3-(3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl)-1H-imidazol-3-ium chloride with a mesoporous SBA-15 silica and then an oxodiperoxomolybdenum complex was immobilized onto the obtained SILP. The resulting material, identified as SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅, was characterized by solid state NMR (¹H, ¹³C and ²⁹Si), and their textural and thermogravimetric properties were determined. The SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ material was investigated as catalyst for the oxidation of methylphenylsulfide, as model reaction, with aqueous hydrogen peroxide as oxidant at room temperature. The presence of the molybdenum species was crucial for achieving good conversions and methanol was selected as the best solvent (conversion of 95 % and selectivity towards sulfoxide 98 %). The optimized reaction conditions were applied for the oxidation of several selected sulfides. In general, good catalytic activity and selectivity to sulfoxide were obtained and, remarkably, the selectivity toward sulfoxide is higher than those observed in the study of the same process carried out in [C₄mim][PF₆] (C₄mim = 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium) and catalyzed by a molecular molybdenum complex, under the same reaction conditions. The importance of the IL-functionalization in the SBA-15 material was evidenced by recycling experiments. The SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ catalyst was used for the sulfoxidation of the methylphenylsulfide substrate for ten reaction cycles without a significant change in conversion, selectivity to sulfoxide and molybdenum content.

1. Introduction

The use of environmentally-benign catalytic processes is a priority of modern chemistry [1,2,3]. For this reason, the search of *greener* processes in traditional organic transformations, which generally employed stoichiometric reagents and volatile solvents, is a challenge. One example of such a process is the oxidation of organic sulfides, which is one of the more important and useful strategies for the synthesis of added value sulfoxides [4,5,6,7,8,9,10]. There are several significant drawbacks of this reaction, as for example: (i) the catalyst nature, its complicated synthesis and/or its metal price often leads to expensive processes; (ii) the overoxidation to sulfones is frequently difficult to prevent; and (iii) the catalyst recycling in homogeneous catalysis is difficult. A possible solution for the latter negative aspect is the immobilization of the catalyst and several alternatives are now available. One of them is the substitution of common organic solvents by ionic liquids (ILs). The catalyst can be solubilized in the IL whilst being immiscible with the extraction solvent. This means that the products can be separated by extraction, allowing the catalyst to be recycled [11,12,13,14,15,16]. A further advanced option is the use of a “heterogenized” type of catalysis using ILs known as Supported Ionic Liquid Phase (SILP) catalysts [17,18,19,20,21]. In these systems, an IL is immobilized on a high-surface area porous solid (by covalent anchoring or by absorption) and a transition-metal complex is dissolved in the thin film of the ionic liquid. The resulting catalyst is a solid with the active species dissolved in the IL phase and behaving as a homogeneous catalyst, thus combining the attractive features of the latter with the benefits of heterogeneous catalysis. Furthermore, SILP-catalysts are good candidates for their application for bioreactors [22,23] and for continuous-flow processes using conventional solvents or supercritical fluids [24,25,26]. For these reasons, the use of SILPs in catalysis is an emergent area and, in particular, several examples of typical oxidation reactions like epoxidation [27], alcohol oxidation [28], and olefin oxidation [29] were recently reported. Sulfide oxidation was also investigated and SILP-catalyzed examples with titanium [30] and tungsten [31] metals are known.

Following our recent research on catalyzed oxidations in non-conventional media [32,33,34,35] and the acquired knowledge on oxodiperoxomolibdenum-catalyzed olefin epoxidation in ionic liquids [36,37,38,39,40] we decided to explore the oxodiperoxomolibdenum-catalyzed sulfide oxidation. In fact, we recently described a green approach to this process using hydrogen peroxide in ILs media [41]. Here, we present the next step in our research and report the preparation and characterization of a SILP based on

mesoporous silica SBA-15, functionalized covalently with an imidazolium-based IL, and the use of this material in the oxidation of organic sulfides. The *green* advantages are: (i) the use of easily available oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes as catalysts, coming from economic and commercial MoO₃, and efficient in oxidation reactions carried out in ILs [36-40]; (ii) the use of cheap and environmentally-benign aqueous hydrogen peroxide as oxidant [42,43]; (iii) favored selectivity to sulfoxide by the heterogeneization [44]; and, (iv) efficient catalyst recycling.

2. Experimental

2.1. General

Synthetic reactions were performed under nitrogen by using Schlenk techniques where necessary. Solvents were purified and dried appropriately prior to use, by standard procedures. Chemicals were obtained from commercial sources and used as supplied. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 883 spectrophotometer (Nujol emulsion in NaCl or KBr plates or in pressed KBr pellets). NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker AMX-300 spectrometer with ¹³C{¹H} and ¹H shifts referenced to the residual solvent signals. All data are reported in ppm downfield from Si(CH₃)₄. Solid state NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker Avance III WB 600 MHz spectrometer. Gas chromatography experiments (GC) were recorded on a Varian CP-3800 Chromatograph with nitrogen as carrier gas, flame ionization detector (FID), and a Varian column, model CP-8741. Elemental analyses (C, H, N) were conducted by the Centro de Investigaciones, Tecnología e Innovación (CITIUS) of the University of Sevilla on an Elemental LECO CHNS 93 analyzer. Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) analysis of the mesoporous samples were carried out by using PanAnalytical X'Pert Pro® diffractometer in the 0.5-4 theta range. Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) were performed on SDTQ60 thermobalance from 30 to 900 °C at a constant heating ramp of 10 °C. min⁻¹ in flow of air.

2.2. Syntheses

1-Methyl-3-(3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl)-1H-imidazol-3-ium chloride, **ImCl**. This compound was prepared by a slight modification of published procedures [20,45,46,47].

(3-chloropropyl)triethoxysilane (30 ml, 0.125 mmol) and 1-methyl-1H-imidazole (10 ml, 0.125 mmol) were mixed and heated at 95 °C with stirring for three days, under nitrogen. The resulting oily mixture was extracted with dry ethyl acetate. The solution was evaporated to dryness affording a yellow viscous oil (36.6 g, 95% yield). This oil was characterized spectroscopically (IR, ^1H and $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR) and the obtained data were similar to those reported in bibliography.

Preparation of mesoporous SBA-15. 9.60 g of Pluronic 123 were dissolved in a mixture of water (225 ml) and 4 M HCl (150 ml) at room temperature. Over this solution 21.4 ml of TEOS was added under vigorous stirring. After aging at 40 °C for 24 h, the final product was obtained after hydrothermal treating at 80 °C for 24 h. The solid product was recovered by filtration, washed with water and ethanol and dried at 110 °C. Finally, the material was calcined at 500 °C for 10 h (1°C/min).

SBA-15 functionalization, SBA-15+ImCl. The mesoporous SBA-15 material (1 g) was heated at 300 °C for 2 h and, after that, a solution of 1-methyl-3-(3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl)-1H-imidazol-3-ium chloride (1.5 g) in dry toluene (5 ml) was added, under nitrogen. The mixture was stirred at 90 °C for 16 h. The resulting solid was isolated by filtration and washed with CH_2Cl_2 . Then, the solid was introduced in a Soxhlet system and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 at reflux for 24 h. A white powder was obtained and air-dried. Experimental elemental analyses: C, 15.52; H, 2.79; N, 5.33 %.

Molybdenum impregnation on SBA-15, SBA-15+MoO5. Over a sample of SBA-15 (100 mg) was added dropwise 100 μL of a 0.250 M aqueous solution of $[\text{MoO}(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$. During the addition, the mixture was manually stirred with a spatula until getting a yellow homogeneous solid.

Molybdenum immobilization onto the functionalized SBA-15 material, SBA-15+ImCl+MoO5. Over a sample of the functionalized SBA-15 material (100 mg), SBA-15+ImCl, was added dropwise 100 μL of a 0.250 M aqueous solution of $[\text{MoO}(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$. During the addition, the mixture was manually stirred with a spatula until to get a yellow homogeneous solid. Experimental elemental analyses: Mo, 1.74; C, 14.79; H, 3.27; N, 5.12 %.

2.3. General procedure for catalytic oxidation of sulfide to sulfoxide

The reactor (a 5 mL vial equipped with a Young valve, containing a stirrer flea, and with the appropriated design for a direct centrifugation) was charged with the solid catalyst (100 mg of SBA-15+ImCl with 100 μ L added of 0.25 M [Mo] solution), the solvent (2 ml, usually methanol), the oxidant (1 mmol, in general 30 % aqueous H₂O₂) and the substrate (1 mmol), in the aforementioned order. The reactor was sealed and the suspension reacted with constant stirring (600 rpm) in a thermostated oil bath (usually at 25 °C) for the desired time (usually 1 h). Upon completion the reactor was immediately cooled to 0 °C and then centrifuged (20 min). The liquid phase was decanted and the solid washed with vigorous stirring with the solvent reaction (2 x 4 ml) and Et₂O (4 ml). These washings were separated by centrifugation and combined with the liquid phase. The solution was evaporated to dryness by using a rotavap. The resulting residue was analysed by GC (by adding 10 ml of Et₂O and 50 μ l of dodecane as internal standard).

2.4. Catalyst recycling

The experimental procedure for the first cycle was conducted as detailed above. After the liquid phase separation and washings, the solid catalyst material was dried under vacuum. The reactor was charged again with the solvent (2 ml), the oxidant (1 mmol) and the substrate (1 mmol) and sealed. The reaction was carried out in the manner described above and analyzed similarly. Experimental elemental analyses (after ten catalytic cycles): Mo, 1.54 %.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of molybdenum-immobilized SBA-15 materials.

The SILP was prepared by reacting 1-methyl-3-(3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl)-1H-imidazol-3-ium chloride with the modified silica according to Scheme 1. Then, the material was treated with an aqueous solution of [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n], prepared as described elsewhere [38], and the catalyst material SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ was obtained (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The ionic liquid grafting is firstly verified by solid state ^1H , $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ and ^{29}Si NMR. In Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 the ^1H and $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectra of all the materials are compared to that of the ionic liquid ImCl. The bonding of the parent ionic liquid ImCl to the solid SBA-15 is clearly confirmed by the almost complete disappearance of the triethoxysilyl signals, both in the ^1H NMR (centered at 1.17, t, and 3.80 ppm, q, for ImCl) and in the $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (singlets at 18.4 and 58.2 ppm for ImCl). All the other signals of the ionic liquid are present in the solids with essentially no shifts with respect to the ImCl. The exception is the signal attributed to the proton of the imidazolium ring attached to the C between two adjacent N-atoms (at 9.76 ppm in the ionic liquid ImCl), which shifts considerably to high field in the ^1H NMR (Fig. 2). This proton situated together with the imidazolium positive charge is the first to be altered by the electrostatic interactions with the negative Si-O network in the SBA-15. The same shift was observed by Martinez et al. for ionic liquid/zeolite composites [48]. The ^{29}Si NMR spectra of the solids were also recorded and a comparison of the synthesized solids with respect SBA-15 is shown in Fig. 3. The SBA-15 spectrum shows the presence of Si in Q₂ [$=\text{Si}(\text{OH})_2$, $\delta \sim -91.2$]; Q₃ [$=\text{Si}(\text{OH})$, $\delta \sim -100.4$] and Q₄ [$=\text{Si}-\text{O}-\text{Si}$, $\delta \sim -109.4$] environment. When the ionic liquid is present the appearance of the signals T₁ [$-\text{Si}(\text{OR})_2\text{R}'$, $\delta \sim -50.2$]; T₂ [$=\text{Si}(\text{OR})\text{R}'$, $\delta \sim -58.3$] and T₃ [$=\text{Si}-\text{R}'$, $\delta \sim -66.0$] is observed and confirms the grafting of the ionic liquid on the SBA-15 surface. In addition a change in the Q₄/Q₃ ratio is observed and indicates that the grafting proceeds through free silanol OH groups. The addition of the molybdenum complex does not imply additional changes in the solids. The NMR analysis of the prepared solids unequivocally point to the successful grafting of the ionic liquids on the surface and preservation of the chemical bonding after the catalyst addition.

Fig. 1. ^1H NMR of the synthesized solids and their comparison with the ionic liquid ImCl.

Fig. 2. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR of the synthesized solids and their comparison with the ionic liquid ImCl.

Fig. 3. ^{29}Si NMR spectra of the synthesized solids.

The original SBA-15 material presents SAXS pattern (Fig. 4) typical for ordered mesoporous structure with three well-resolved peaks indexed as (100) (110) and (200) attributed to two-dimensional hexagonal P6mm symmetry. The ionic liquid grafting and the subsequent catalyst impregnation do not modify the SBA-15 structure and the same SAXS pattern is observed. However, slight shift to lower degrees is perceived and could be attributed to some loss of the mesoporous order.

Fig. 4. SAXS patterns of the prepared solid samples.

The textural properties of the solids are summarized in Table 1. All solids present type IV isotherms (not shown) typical for mesoporous materials. The hysteresis type H2 indicates the presence of uniform ink-bottle like pores. The ionic liquid grafting decreases drastically the initial SBA-15 specific surface area, due to the pore filling and subsequent pore volume diminution. In the same time the pore size increases indicating a preferential grafting of the ionic liquid in smaller pores.

Table 1

Selected textural properties of the prepared solids.

Sample	Specific Surface Area, m^2/g	Pore size, nm	Pore volume, cm^3
SBA-15	733	4.8	0.88
SBA-15+ImCl	101	6.4	0.16
SBA-15+ImCl+MoO5	83	6.6	0.14

The thermal stability of the SBA-15+ImCl and SBA-15+ImCl+MoO5 materials were analyzed by TGA analysis (Fig. 5). The initial weight loss at low temperature (<100 °C) is recognized as physisorbed solvents removal. The ionic liquid removal starts at around 250 °C

and it is completed in three steps at 700 °C accompanied with heat release. The quantity of the grafted ionic liquid could be estimated as 27 wt %. The addition of the molybdenum complex does not change significantly the thermal profile of the SBA-15+ImCl. A shift to lower temperature of the ionic liquid removal is observed and ascribed to the promoted oxidation activity by the presence of the molybdenum complex.

Fig. 5. Thermogravimetric analysis of the samples SBA-15+ImCl and SBA-15+ImCl+MoO5.

All the characterization shows the preservation of the SBA-15 structure during the ionic liquid grafting and catalyst deposition. The resulting final material inherits the well-ordered pore structure of the SBA-15 material and the fairly good thermal stability of the ionic liquid.

3.2. Catalytic oxidation of sulfides to sulfoxides with hydrogen peroxide.

In order to select the best reaction conditions, the resulting catalyst SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ was tested in the oxidation of methylphenylsulfide, as model reaction, using aqueous hydrogen peroxide as oxidant (Scheme 2). Table 2 shows the results obtained for this reaction with several solvents and several catalysts. Some reaction conditions were similar with respect those optimized in the study of the same process carried out in ILs [41].

Scheme 2

Table 2

Oxidation of PhSMe with hydrogen peroxide under several reaction conditions ^a

Entry	Catalyst	Solvent	Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%)
1	-	MeOH	19	94
2	SBA-15	MeOH	36	100
3	SBA-15+ImCl	MeOH	32	96
4	SBA-15+MoO ₅	MeOH	82	98
5	SBA-15+ImCl+MoO ₅	Cl ₂ CH ₂	15	94
6	SBA-15+ImCl+MoO ₅	Et ₂ O	57	92
7	SBA-15+ImCl+MoO ₅	THF	94	91
8	SBA-15+ImCl+MoO ₅	MeOH	95	98

^a Reaction conditions: Mo content of catalyst:sulfide ratio 0.025:1, sulfide 1.0 mmol, solvent 2.0 mL, sulfide:aqueous hydrogen peroxide 30% ratio 1:1, time 1h, T 298 K. After extraction with Et₂O (4 x 5 mL), the conversion and selectivity calculated by GC (50 μl of dodecane as internal standard).

The reaction proceeded even in the absence of catalyst (entry 1), in agreement with previous results [43,49], but conversions were limited to less than 20 % in 1 h. The conversion was increased slightly (ca. 35 %, entries 2-3) by carrying the reaction in the presence of mesoporous SBA-15 or the same material functionalized with the ionic liquid, SBA-15+ImCl. The latter was not unexpected because other ionic liquid-functionalized SBA-15 materials were reported as heterogeneous catalyst in several organic reactions [50]. The

presence of the molybdenum species was crucial for achieving good conversions (higher than 80 %, entry 4) as was demonstrated with the Mo-impregnated material, SBA-15+MoO₅ (entry 4) [51,52,53]. This result is comparable with a related system in which molybdate was immobilized in a magnetic nanoparticle coated by a functionalized silica [54]. The best catalyst/solvent combination of Table 2 was the use of the SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ catalyst with methanol as solvent (entry 8). For this combination, a conversion of 95 % and a high selectivity towards sulfoxide (98 %) were observed. Lower conversions were observed with other solvents (entries 5-6), while THF was discarded as solvent (entry 7) because severe leaching was found when the catalyst was recycled.

In agreement with the conclusion obtained from Table 2, the optimized reaction for the oxidation of sulfide to sulfoxide should be carried out using the SILP SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ as catalyst, with a 1:1:0.025 ratio of sulfide substrate:H₂O₂:catalyst in methanol at 298 K for 1 h. To generalize the developed procedure, several selected sulfides were thus analyzed under these reaction conditions. The results obtained in this study are shown in Table 3. In general, good catalytic activity and selectivity to sulfoxide were obtained for the alkylarylsulfide substrates (entries 2-6), being the diphenylsulfide more difficult to oxidize (entry 1). For example, the methylphenylsulfide substrate (entry 2) was oxidized to the corresponding sulfoxide with similar conversion and selectivity that related peroxotungstate species on SBA-15 [55] or on SILP [31]. Also, the activity of molybdate immobilized in a magnetic nanoparticle coated by functionalized silica is comparable to our results and, for instance, 4-chlorothioanisole was oxidized for such a system in 4.5 h with 92 % of conversion [54]. Remarkably, in all the cases shown in Table 3 the selectivity to sulfoxide is higher than those observed in the study of the same process carried out in [C₄min][PF₆] and catalyzed by [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(Mepz)₂] complex (Mepz = methylpyrazole) under the same reaction conditions [41].

The removal of sulphur-containing compounds from fuels is a topic of extraordinary interest in *green* chemistry. One of the better available methods for sulphur removal is the oxidation of sulphur-containing compounds (in particular, thiophene derivatives such as dibenzothiophene and benzothiophene), followed by extraction of the oxidized products [56,57,58,59,60]. In this respect, several research teams [61,62], including us [41], have focused on sulfide oxidation in ionic liquids, which were used both as reaction media and as extractants. With these precedents we decided to investigate the SILP-catalyzed oxidation of several thiophene derivatives (Table 4). The results of the same process carried out in [C₄min][PF₆] were also included for the appropriate comparison.

Table 3SILP-molybdenum catalyzed oxidation of several sulfides with hydrogen peroxide ^a

Entry	Sulfide	Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%) ^b
1	Diphenylsulfide	48	93 (83)
2	Methylphenylsulfide	95	98 (96)
3	Methyl- <i>p</i> -tolylsulfide	96	95 (85)
4	4-Chlorothioanisole	77	99 (87)
5	4-Bromothioanisole	94	96 (83)
6	Ethylphenylsulfide	92	91 (73)

^a Reaction conditions: SILP catalyst: SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅, Mo content of catalyst:sulfide ratio 0.025:1, sulfide 1.0 mmol, MeOH 2.0 mL, 1 mmol aqueous H₂O₂ 30 %, time 1 h. After extraction with Et₂O (4 x 5 mL), the conversion and selectivity were calculated by GC (50 µl of dodecane as internal standard). ^b The results shown in parenthesis were obtained from the reaction carried out in [C₄min][PF₆] with the [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(Mepz)₂] catalyst under the same reaction conditions (reference 41).

As expected for a dialkyl sulfide substrate, the oxidation of the tetrahydrothiophene catalyzed by the SILP (entry 1) was very efficient (97 % conversion) with complete selectivity to sulfoxide with the employed 1:1 sulfide:H₂O₂ ratio. The conversion was of the same order that those observed in [C₄min][PF₆], although again the selectivity in the IL medium was lower than that found for the SILP system. On the contrary, the oxidation of dibenzothiophene (entry 2) and benzothiophene (entry 6) proceeded worse with the SILP catalyst in methanol (conversions of 1 and 43 %, respectively) in comparison with the reactions carried in [C₄min][PF₆]. For these substrates other solvents, like EtOH, ⁿPrOH and ⁿBuOH, were investigated (entries 3-5, 7-9) with the SILP catalyst and very low conversions were detected. Although a detailed study was not performed, it may be understood that a phase transfer catalysis process is responsible for this behavior. Mass diffusion, substrate solubility and solvent nature were effects that influence the catalytic performance of the SILP catalyst for these substrates. Conversely to others [63], benzothiophene was found to be more easily oxidized with hydrogen peroxide in methanol (entry 6) than dibenzothiophene (entry 2). The performance of SILP catalyst in benzothiophene oxidation was similar to related metal catalyst on silica [64], while for dibenzothiophene oxidation was worse than other Mo-silica systems [65]. In any case, the SILP option was not especially adequate for the thiophene-derivatives removal by oxidation with hydrogen peroxide, because the use of [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] catalyst in [C₄min][PF₆] produced complete conversion and selectivity to sulfone for all the substrates investigated, under the reaction conditions stated in Table 4.

Table 4Molybdenum catalyzed oxidation of several thiophene derivatives with hydrogen peroxide ^a

Entry	Sulfide	SILP catalyst ^b			Catalyst [Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (Mepz) ₂] ^d		Catalyst [Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n] ^d	
		Solvent ^c	Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%)	Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%)	Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%)
1	Tetrahydrothiophene	MeOH	97	100	95	79	93 (100 °)	55 (0 °)
2	Dibenzothiophene	MeOH	1	71	66	2	67 (100 °)	1 (0 °)
3	Dibenzothiophene	EtOH	3	51	-	-	-	-
4	Dibenzothiophene	ⁿ PrOH	2	71	-	-	-	-
5	Dibenzothiophene	ⁿ BuOH	0	-	-	-	-	-
6	Benzothiophene	MeOH	43	86	63	1	16 (100 ^f)	10 (0 ^f)
7	Benzothiophene	EtOH	2	100	-	-	-	-
8	Benzothiophene	ⁿ PrOH	4	100	-	-	-	-
9	Benzothiophene	ⁿ BuOH	0	-	-	-	-	-

^a Reaction conditions: Mo content of catalyst:sulfide ratio 0.025:1, sulfide 1.0 mmol, 1 mmol aqueous H₂O₂ 30 %. After extraction with Et₂O (4 x 5 mL), the conversion and selectivity were calculated by GC (50 µl of dodecane as internal standard). ^b SILP catalyst: SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅, time 1 h. ^c Solvent: 2.0 mL. ^d Reactions carried out with the Mo-catalyst, under the same reaction conditions, solvent: [C₄min][PF₆] 2 mL, time 1h (reference 41). ^e Reactions carried out with a 1:3 sulfide:H₂O₂ ratio for 18 h with complete oxidation to sulfone. ^f Reactions carried out with a 1:3 sulfide:H₂O₂ ratio for 18 h at 60 °C with complete oxidation to sulfone.

3.3. Catalyst recycling

One of the main advantages for using immobilized catalysts in SILPs was to study the possibility of recycling. This option was then investigated by performing the sulfoxidation of the methylphenylsulfide substrate. Interestingly, the recycled catalyst could be used for at least ten reaction cycles without a significant change in conversion or selectivity to sulfoxide. Furthermore, the molybdenum content after the ten cycles remains approximately constant (1.54 % *versus* the initial 1.74 %), confirming thus the absence of significant leaching. The results, shown in Fig. 6, clearly confirmed the practical reusability of the catalyst material, under the described reaction conditions. The importance of the IL-functionalization in the SBA-15 material was evidenced by the recycling experiment carried out with the SBA-15+MoO₅, namely the catalyst obtained by impregnation of the oxidiperoxo-complex. In this case, although the conversion is high in the first cycles (*ca.* 80 %), the molybdenum content appreciably decreases after five cycles (0.014 %).

Fig. 6. Conversion and selectivity to methylphenylsulfoxide (%) for ten catalytic cycles of the oxidation of methylphenylsulfide with hydrogen peroxide catalyzed by SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ (for reaction conditions see Experimental).

4. Conclusions

The SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ solid material was obtained, by immobilization of an oxidiperoxomolybdenum complex onto the ionic liquid thin film of the SILP SBA-15+ImCl,

and conveniently characterized. The catalytic performance of this material was investigated and excellent conversions and selectivity towards sulfoxide were observed in the oxidation reaction of sulfoxides with aqueous hydrogen peroxide. The presence of the molybdenum species was crucial for achieving this good activity and its heterogeneization, by immobilization onto the SILP, was essential to achieve higher selectivity toward sulfoxide than that observed in the homogeneous study, under the same reaction conditions. Methanol was selected as the best solvent for the reaction and the importance of mass diffusion, substrate solubility and solvent nature effects were evidenced when low conversions were detected for other solvent alcohols. Although a detailed study was not performed, a phase transfer catalysis process was proposed for explaining this behavior. The SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ catalyst recycling was very efficient. Thus, for the sulfoxidation of the methylphenylsulfide substrate, ten reaction cycles were carried out without a significant change in conversion or selectivity to sulfoxide. Moreover, the absence of significant leaching after the recycling was established through the constancy observed in the molybdenum content. The importance of the IL-functionalization in the SBA-15 material was evidenced by comparing the recycling experiments carried out with the SBA-15+MoO₅, namely the catalyst without ionic liquid, in which molybdenum leaching was detected. Summarizing, SBA-15+ImCl+MoO₅ material is a *green* catalyst with several advantages. It was obtained from economic and easily available oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes and selective sulfoxidation was achieved by using cheap and environmentally-benign aqueous hydrogen peroxide as oxidant, while the selectivity towards sulfoxide and the catalyst recycling was favored by heterogeneization.

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References

- [1] R. A. Sheldon, *Chem. Commun.* (2008) 3352.
- [2] M. Poliakoff, P. Licence, *Nature* 450 (2007) 810.
- [3] P. T. Anastas, J. C. Warner, *Green Chemistry: Theory and Practice*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1998.
- [4] G. E. O'Mahony, A. Ford, A. R. Maguire, *J. Sulfur Chem.* 34 (2013) 301.
- [5] R. Bentley, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 34 (2005) 609.
- [6] I. Fernández, N. Khair, *Chem. Rev.* 103 (2003) 3651.
- [7] A. M. Khenkin, R. J. Neumann, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 124 (2002) 4198.
- [8] E. Wojaczynska, J. Wojaczynski, *Chem. Rev.* 110 (2010) 4303.
- [9] C. Bolm, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 237 (2003) 245.
- [10] M. A. Fascione, S. J. Adshead, P. K. Mandal, C. A. Kilner, A. G. Leach, W. B. Turnbull, *Chem. Eur. J.* 18 (2012) 2987.
- [11] J. P. Hallett, T. Welton, *Chem. Rev.* 111 (2011) 3508.
- [12] P. Wasserscheid, T. Welton, *Ionic Liquids in Synthesis*, Wiley-VCH, 2003.
- [13] V. I. Parvulescu, C. Hardacre, *Chem. Rev.* 107 (2007) 2615.
- [14] D. Betz, P. Altmann, M. Cokoja, W. A. Herrmann, F. E. Kühn, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 255 (2011) 1518.
- [15] J. Muzart, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 348 (2006) 275.
- [16] L. Gharnati, M. Döring, U. Arnold, *Current Org. Synth.* 6 (2009) 342.
- [17] A. Riisager, R. Fehrmann, M. Haumann, P. Wasserscheid, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* (2006) 695.
- [18] B. Ni, A. D. Headly, *Chem. Eur. J.* 16 (2010) 4426.
- [19] C. Van Doorslaer, J. Wahlen, P. Mertens, K. Binnemans, D. De Vos, *Dalton Trans.* 39 (2010) 8377.
- [20] C. P. Mehnert, R. A. Cook, N. C. Dispenziere, M. Afeworki, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 124 (2002) 12932.
- [21] Y. Gu, G. Li, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 351 (2009) 817.
- [22] P. Lozano, E. García-Verdugo, R. Piamtongkam, N. Karbass, T. De Diego, M. I. Burguete, S. V. Luis, J. L. Iborra, *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 349 (2007) 1077.
- [23] P. Lozano, E. García-Verdugo, N. Karbass, K. Montague, T. De Diego, M. I. Burguete, S. V. Luis, *Green Chem.* 12 (2010) 1803.

- [24] S. Martín, R. Porcar, E. Peris, M. I. Burguete, E. García-Verdugo, S. V. Luis, *Green Chem.* 16 (2014) 1639.
- [25] M. I. Burguete, E. García-Verdugo, I. Garcia-Villar, F. Gelat, P. Licence, S. V. Luis, V. Sans, *J. Catal.* 269 (2010) 150.
- [26] M. I. Burguete, H. Erythropel, E. García-Verdugo, S. V. Luis, V. Sans, *Green Chem.* 10 (2008) 401.
- [27] L.-L. Lou, K. Fu, F. Ding, W. Zhou, X. Peng, S. Liu, *Tetrahedron Lett.* 47 (2006) 6513.
- [28] S. Sahoo, P. Kumar, F. Lefebvre, S. B. Halligudi, *Tetrahedron Lett.* 49 (2008) 4865.
- [29] G. Liu, M. Hou, J. Song, Z. Zhang, T. Wu, B. Han, *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* 316 (2010) 90.
- [30] S. Sahoo, P. Kumar, F. Lefebvre, S. B. Halligudi, *J. Catal.* 262 (2009) 111.
- [31] X.-Y. Shi, J.-F. Wei, *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* 280 (2008) 142.
- [32] M. Herbert, F. Montilla, A. Galindo, *Dalton Trans.* 39 (2010) 900.
- [33] M. Herbert, F. Montilla, A. Galindo, *Polyhedron* 29 (2010) 3287.
- [34] M. Herbert, F. Montilla, A. Galindo, *Organometallics* 28 (2009) 2855.
- [35] M. Herbert, F. Montilla, A. Galindo, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* 10 (2007) 735.
- [36] M. Herbert, F. Montilla, A. Galindo, *Catal. Commun.* 8 (2007) 987.
- [37] M. Herbert, F. Montilla, R. Moyano, A. Pastor, E. Álvarez, A. Galindo, *Polyhedron* 28 (2009) 3929.
- [38] M. Herbert, F. Montilla, A. Galindo, *J. Mol. Catal. A: Chem.* 338 (2011) 111.
- [39] M. Herbert, E. Álvarez, D. J. Cole-Hamilton, F. Montilla, A. Galindo, *Chem. Commun.* 46 (2010) 5933.
- [40] M. Herbert, F. Montilla, A. Galindo, R. Moyano, A. Pastor, E. Álvarez, *Dalton Trans.* 40 (2011) 5210.
- [41] C. J. Carrasco, F. Montilla, E. Álvarez, C. Mealli, G. Manca, A. Galindo, *Dalton Trans.* 43 (2014) 13711.
- [42] J.-E. Backvall, Ed., *Modern Oxidation Methods*, 2nd Ed., Wiley, 2010.
- [43] K. Kaczorowska, Z. Kolarska, K. Mitka, P. Kowalski, *Tetrahedron* 61 (2005) 8315.
- [44] See for example: F. Batigaglia, M. Zaldini-Hernandes, A. G. Ferreira, I. Malvestiti, Q. B. Cass, *Tetrahedron* 57 (2001) 9669.
- [45] B. Gadenne, P. Hesemann, J. J. E. Moreau, *Chem. Commun.* (2004) 1768.
- [46] Y. S. Chi, J. K. Lee, S. Lee, I. S. Choi, *Langmuir* 20 (2004) 3024.
- [47] F. Wang, Z. Zhang, J. Yang, L. Wang, Y. Lin, Y. Wei, *Fuel* 107 (2013) 394.

- [48] J. M. Martínez Blanes, B. M. Szyja, F. Romero-Sarria, M. A. Centeno, E. J. M. Hensen, J. A. Odriozola, S. Ivanova, *Chem. Eur. J.* 19 (2013) 2122.
- [49] J. Drabowicz, M. Mikołajczyk, *Synth. Commun.* 11 (1981) 1025.
- [50] L.-W. Xu, M.-S. Yang, J.-X. Jiang, H.-Y. Qiu, G.-Q. Lai, *Central Eur. J. Chem.* 5 (2007) 1073.
- [51] For other Mo-containing SBA-15 catalysts see for example: (a) S. Budhi, C. Peeraphatdit, S. Pylypenko, Vy H. T. Nguyen, E. A. Smith, B. G. Trewyn, *Appl. Catal. A: Gen.* 475 (2014) 469 and references 52 and 53.
- [52] J. Liu, L. Yu, Z. Zhao, Y. Chen, P. Zhu, C. Wang, Y. Luo, C. Xu, A. Duan, G. Jiang, *J. Catal.* 285 (2012) 134.
- [53] Z. Huang, W. Bensch, W. Sigle, P. A. van Aken, L. Kienle, T. Vitoya, H. Modrow, T. Ressler, *J. Mater. Sci.* 43 (2008) 244.
- [54] A. Bayat, M. Shakourina-Fard, M. M. Hashemi, *Catal. Commun.* 52 (2014) 16.
- [55] B. Karimi, M. Khorasani, *ACS catal.* 3 (2013) 1657.
- [56] L. F. Ramirez-Verduzco, E. Torres-Garcia, R. Gomez-Quintana, V. Gonzalez-Pena, F. Murrieta-Guevara, *Catal. Today* 98 (2004) 289.
- [57] H. Y. Lü, J. B. Gao, Z. X. Jiang, F. Jing, Y. X. Yang, G. Wang, C. Li, *J. Catal.* 239 (2006) 369.
- [58] H. Lü, Y. Zhang, Z. Jiang, C. Li, *Green Chem.* 12 (2010) 1954.
- [59] W. Zhu, H. Li, X. Jiang, Y. Yan, J. Lu, J. Xia, *Energy Fuels* 21 (2007) 2514.
- [60] J. L. García-Gutiérrez, G. A. Fuentes, M. E. Hernández-Terán, P. García, F. Murrieta-Guevara, F. Jiménez-Cruz, *Appl. Catal. A: Gen.* 334 (2008) 366.
- [61] B. Zhang, S. Li, S. Yue, M. Cokoja, M.-D. Zhou, S.-L. Zang, F. E. Kühn, *J. Organomet. Chem.* 744 (2013) 108.
- [62] W. Zhu, H. Li, X. Jiang, Y. Yan, J. Lu, L. He, J. Xia, *Green Chem.* 10 (2008) 641.
- [63] M. Ciclosi, C. Dinoi, L. Gonsalvi, M. Peruzzini, E. Manoury, R. Poli, *Organometallics* 27 (2008) 2281.
- [64] See for example: A. M. Cojocariu, P. H. Mutin, E. Dumitriu, A. Aboulaich, A. Vioux, F. Fajula, V. Hulea, *Catal. Today* 157 (2010) 270.
- [65] See for example: J. Chang, A. Wang, J. Liu, X. Li, Y. Hu, *Catal. Today* 149 (2010) 122.